

Voice of child passenger: Word association test approach to child-friendly airport

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Article Info	Abstract
RESEARCH ARTICLE	<p>This study was conducted to reveal the perceptions of students from 13-18 age groups about the concept of 'child-friendly airport'. A total of 371 students studying in Istanbul in the 2022-2023 academic year participated in the study. A phenomenological design was used in the study and the data were analyzed using the content analysis technique for the words coded for each theme. The NVIVO 11 program was used for word frequency analysis and word clouds were created. In the study, a word association test was applied with the "child-friendly airport" given to the students as a stimulus concept. The following questions were sought to be answered in the research: 1) Which words do students between the ages of 13-18 use to evoke the concept of "child-friendly airport"? 2) Considering their common characteristics, under which themes can the words related to the concept of "child-friendly airport" be grouped? In this study, the words used by the students were analyzed under four themes: Sociability, access/linkages, comfort/image, uses/activities. participants derived most words for the comfort/image theme and the least for the access/linkages theme. Among the most recurring words, "free service" "hygiene" "playground" and "colorful" are noteworthy. Given the lack of research on the child-friendly airport, it is believed that exploring it in terms of cognitive structure and conceptual meaning will make a significant contribution to the relevant literature, both in terms of content and the data collection technique used. Our findings and can help to develop child- and family-friendly airport concepts for travel practices.</p>
<p>Keywords: Child-friendly airport Word Association Test Age group</p>	
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1. Introduction

Over the past 30 to 40 years, airports have evolved from being infrastructure providers providing public services to an approach that aims to meet the needs of all stakeholders. The modern airport management approach adopts a passenger- and value-driven management approach (Chen et al. 2015). While passengers are an important stakeholder category in a value-based management approach, the demands and needs of sub-stakeholder categories such as children also become important. The passenger-centric model supports the design of passenger-centric airports and the translation of passenger needs and perceptions into improved services (Wredja, 2017; Rodriguez-Valencia et al. 2024). Different types of passengers are known to have different expectations and use airport facilities differently, affecting airport perceptions and experiences (Bunchongchit and Wattanacharoensil, 2021). From this perspective, child-friendly airports can be defined as places that offer sustainable child-friendly policies, facilities, play areas and services that are

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adapted to the specific needs of families travelling with children. A child-friendly airport reflects the quality and quantity of child- and family-friendly initiatives at an airport. However, studies on the travel satisfaction of parent-child groups are still very rare (Wu & Wang, 2019). In summary, the relationship between children and airports is under-researched, under-theorised and under-utilised. Given the lack of research on the child-friendly airport, it is believed that exploring it in terms of cognitive structure and conceptual meaning will make a significant contribution to the relevant literature, both in terms of content and the data collection technique used. In this study, we investigate children's perceptual and conceptual schemas of 'child-friendly airports'. Our findings can reveal children's conceptual connotations by associating them with words, and can help to develop child- and family-friendly airport concepts for travel practices. In our research, children's perceptions of the concept of "child-friendly airport" between the ages of 13 and 18 will be assessed using the Independent Word Association Test. How do children perceive and understand a 'child-friendly airport'? There is a need to integrate thinking and understanding about the changing nature of families travelling with children from a child's perspective. The key concepts of a child-friendly airport are addressed from a word association perspective.

2. Theoretical Background

Researchers try to understand passengers' expectations and perceptions by considering a set of criteria or service attributes. Thus, the critical issues required to provide a superior service experience are identified, and when these are provided, customer satisfaction and perceived value increase (Pamucar et al., 2021). Suárez-Alemán and Jiménez (2016) argue that passenger evaluations may also include implicit evaluations of airport management characteristics and features not directly observable. In order to uncover the implicit evaluations mentioned in the literature, there are an increasing number of qualitative studies investigating user perceptions, satisfaction, expectations, positive and negative emotions and using user comments. Online sites have made users' voices louder and stronger in relation to service providers. This applies to airports as well (Gitto and Mancuso, 2017; Lee and Yu, 2018; Nghiêm-Phu and Suter, 2018). Well-known online review sites for the airport industry include Google Maps, the Skytrax website, airport Facebook and X channels, where passengers can leave comments and/or ratings about their airport experience after their journey (Lee and Yu, 2018; Martin-Domingo et al. 2019; Bakir et al. 2022a). Some existing studies suggest that airport management companies can also use blogs to better meet the needs and satisfaction of their customers. However, effective analysis and mining methods are needed to extract customer opinions from such platforms, as the data (text) from such online sources is mostly in an unstructured form (Barakat et al., 2021).

Bogicevic et al. (2013) examined passenger reviews published on Skytrax (www.airlinequality.com) determined service quality attributes according to the frequency of words. They conceptualized the most frequent words with high star ratings as satisfactory, and the most frequent words with low ratings as unsatisfactory. The visualisation helped to discover words that express passengers' complaints and likes. The most common words for highly satisfied passengers related to different categories such as time, friendly, efficient, clean, nice, beautiful, shops, good and easy. Passengers' perceptions of non-aviation services are mostly influenced by food and beverage and shopping area, while their perceptions of aviation services are mostly influenced by check-in, baggage claim and security control procedures (Gitto and Mancuso, 2017). The things that passengers are most satisfied with at airports are cleanliness and a pleasant environment to spend time, while the things they are most dissatisfied with are security checks, confusing signage and poor food options. (Bogicevic et al. 2013). Passengers do not appreciate any additional experience (e.g., aesthetic and hedonic activities) when the basic processes (e.g., basic/main processes at the airport) and human interactions are not satisfactory (Wattanacharoensil et al. ,2017). Lee and Yu (2018) conducted a word frequency analysis to examine the comments on Google Maps. They found that the most frequently mentioned topics by passengers were Free Wi-Fi, easy way finding, variety of facilities, beautiful, clean, modern. The results also show that the relative importance of service quality attributes to passengers varies depending on the size of the airport. Passengers in small airports attach the most importance to Transportation to/from the city, cleanliness, courtesy, passengers in medium-sized airports pay more attention to Food, shops than others, and passengers in larger airports pay more attention to Variety of facilities, ambiance than others. In the study conducted by Inversini (2017), it was found that the activities carried out by passengers while at the airport were related to the main activities of personal relaxation and

spending time (e.g. shopping, eating, coffee, reading) and checking the information provided by the airport (e.g. gate). Booranakittipinyo et al (2024) analyzed passengers' tweets and created word clouds consisting of the top three words that passengers most frequently commented on regarding airports. Comments included helpful staff, pleasant atmosphere, delays, long drive through airports, long queues at security checkpoints, messy airport and lack of parking. For example, Brisbane International Airport had the highest percentage of positive opinions about free Wi-Fi.

Henderson et al (2024) investigate the brand associations that air travellers form with airports and which associations are important when choosing between airports. Passengers' perceptions of airports vary depending on passenger types and the preferences of each segmentation (Fodness and Murray, 2007). The industry is aware that passengers' expectations and experiences of the airport vary according to the type of passenger (for example, those with children). Knowledge of passenger needs and opinions requires the same level of insight and assessment for each person, regardless of age group and purpose of use. In this context, being able to identify needs of different segment passengers will provide airport managers with more insights and thus benefit their strategic decisions (Wattanacharoensil et al. 2016; Bunchongchit and Wattanacharoensil, 2021).

Cao, Li and Zhang (2023), The importance of assessing service satisfaction and prioritising areas for improvement from the passenger perspective has been highlighted. It has been highlighted that an enjoyable experience at the airport can lead to positive attitudes such as intention to reuse the airport, increased non-aeronautical revenue and competitive advantage (Ali, Kim and Ryu, 2016; Han, Yu and Kim, 2018; Bezerra and Gomes, 2019; Antwi et al. 2020; Allen et al. 2021; Ginting and Pamuraharjo, 2024). Indeed, understanding passenger segmentation can help identify differences between passenger groups and support service customisation strategies (Bock, Mangus, & Folse, 2016; Freathy & O'Connell, 2012). Airports are implementing child-friendly airport practices to provide the best customer experience for the family and child passenger segment, particularly in the context of children's rights and recognition of children as citizens. However, 'child-friendly airport' is not comprehensively defined and conceptualized.

Children cannot be considered as a homogeneous group in research. When planning child-friendly airports, the age of children makes a significant difference as they have different needs at different stages of development (infancy to adolescence) (Schänzel & Yeoman, 2014). When children enter adolescence (between 12 and 17 years), they are capable of stronger logical thinking and scientific reasoning and are considered to be in the early stages of adulthood (Coleman et al., 2007; Coleman, 2011). Therefore, he believes that adolescents begin to form their own motivations and expectations about travelling (Decrop, 2005). The relationships that travellers have with airports are important in terms of which are important and why when choosing between airports (Henderson et al. 2024). Although there are studies in the literature for people travelling for different reasons (business, leisure, visiting friends and relatives) and for mixed groups (nationality, gender, age, occupation) using airport terminals (Hong et al. 2020), there is no research on the perceptions of child passengers in relation to the Child Friendly Airport concept.

3. Methodology

Gray et al. (2009), explain that language is central to our knowledge construction and is therefore intrinsically linked to our 'being' and 'action'. Exploring language as both a means of meaning-making and a means of supporting shared participation is critical to the research process. The independent word association test is based on the result that the concepts related to the stimulus word independently reveal individuals' perceptions of this word without limiting the ideas that come to mind (Bahar et al., 1999; Sato and James, 1999; Derman and Eilks, 2016). Content analysis methods will be used in the evaluation of the data collected by using the "Independent Word Association Test" to learn the perceptions and expectations of children aged 13-18 about the concept of "Child Friendly Airport". Seggie and Bayyurt (2015) stated that content analysis can be used to identify and quantify the presence of words, concepts, themes, idioms, characters or sentences in one or many texts.

In the literature, the concept of sense of place has been applied in the context of airports to create meanings and strengthen one's cultural connection to a place (Losekoot and Wright, 2011). All attempts to create a

sense of place at the airport can enhance the passenger airport experience and cause passengers to cognitively connect with place (Wattanacharoensil et al. 2016). The Public Spaces Project (PPS) Diagram of Place model was used to thematize the research data. The words produced by the participants regarding the concept of "child-friendly airport" were classified according to the dimensions of the PPS Place Diagram Model. Since it is based on the question "What Makes a Great Place?" (PPS, 2023) emphasized in this model, the theme dimensions are as follows: (1) Sociability; (2) Uses and Activities; (3) Access and Linkages; and (4) Comfort and Image (PPS, 2007).

Sociability: Sociability describes an interaction that is both pleasant and joyful. This interaction is the interaction of people in society. In this case, sociability is an important quality for creating a good place. **Uses and Activities:** Activities are a must for every place. People think of an activity everywhere they go. After all, having something to do gives people a reason to return to a place in the future. Therefore, a good place has more activities and people have the opportunity to be there. **Access and Linkages:** Access is defined as how easily a place can be reached or entered. Linkages are classified as distributing different assets of the same place differently. **Comfort and Image:** A place that is comfortable and presents itself well will have a good image. This is the most important key for people to prefer that place. A comfortable place is one where it is easy to spend time. It is a combination of visible qualities and many different elements that make people feel included.

Answers will be sought to the following Sub-Problem Statements:

1. What are the words associated with the concept of child-friendly airport?
2. Under which conceptual themes can these words be grouped in terms of their common characteristics?

3.1. Sample of the study

Since there is no age-categorized data on the customers using the airport in Turkey, purposeful sampling, technique was used as the sampling method. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2008), the type of "purposeful sampling" is related to the easier inclusion of individuals or groups to be studied in the research process or the easier access to them. In social sciences, the acceptable sample size for a population of 50,000 people is expressed as 381 (+0.05 sampling error) (Yazıcıoğlu and Erdoğan, 2004; Keklik, 2016; Kadioglu, 2021). Therefore, the population in this study is 43,290 people according to MEB (2018) Data (The number of students attending secondary and middle education schools in Avcılar District). In Istanbul for the 13-18 age group, the population was 43,290 people and a sample size of 381 was reached (the research was conducted under pandemic conditions) and 371 data were evaluated within the scope of the study due to data losses. Individuals acquire concepts through their experiences (Gürkan et al. 2020). For this reason, students who have used Istanbul Airport, which is making practices on becoming a child-friendly airport, in the last six months were included in the study.

3.1.1. Data collection process

The "Independent Vocabulary Association Test" form was administered to students attending secondary and middle schools in Avcılar District of Istanbul province within one class hour between 14.02.2022 - 30.05.2022 in approximately 20 minutes by the researchers with the necessary explanations.

3.1.2. Data collection tool

The Vocabulary Association Test can be used to identify the key concepts related to a subject and what associations these concepts create. In this test, students are asked to write the concepts that they associate with the given key concept related to the specified topic. Thus, word association test can be used as an alternative measurement tool in contrast to traditional methods (Bahar et al., 1999; Aitchison 2003; Nissen and Henriksen 2006).

In order to apply the test, the stimulus concept is determined by the researcher. Students are asked to write the answer words that come to their minds in the given time for the stimulus concept (Bahar and Özatlı 2003). In this study, "Child Friendly Airport" was used as a stimulus key concept. After the necessary explanations about the measurement tool were made, the participants were asked to write down 10 words that the key concept reminded them of within 30 seconds. This time given to the participants was determined based on previous studies (Karakuş et al., 2018; Ustaoglu and Aytaç, 2014; Keskin et al., 2017; Doğan and

Onat, 2024). The reason for giving students a certain amount of time is to minimize the risk of chain responses. Thus, the participants were asked to go back to the key concept after writing each word, read it again, and write the word that the key concept reminded them of. Otherwise, it may be possible to be affected by the new word (Kurt and Ekici, 2013a, 2013b). In the second stage, they were asked to write one sentence in 20 seconds using any key concept they wrote about the given stimulus concept.

3.1.3. Data analysis

The content analysis technique was used to analyze the data to create a model of the participants' cognitive structures related to "Child Friendly Airport". The content analysis technique was used for the words coded for each theme. The NVIVO 11 program was used for word frequency analysis and word clouds were created (Özdaşlı ve Çelikkol).

For the children's responses, the researcher and another expert (Measurement and Evaluation Expert) coded independently of each other. Afterwards, 3137 codings, including 4 disciplines and 105 words, emerged from these codings. The following equation was used to calculate consistency:

$$\text{Consistency} = \text{Number of agreements} / \text{total coding} \times 100$$

A total of 2903 codes were reconciled. When substituted in the equation, $(2903/3137) \times 100 = 92.5\%$ consensus was achieved. When the literature is examined, it can be stated that the coding consistency is high, since the agreement percentage of 70% and above is considered reliable (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The 234 words that were coded differently by the two coders were presented to the third expert and included in the research in line with the opinion of the third expert. The contents were coded by two researchers and cross-checked by the third expert to ensure coding reliability before the categories were finalized (Baltacı, 2017).

The data obtained from the independent word association test were collected under 4 different themes in the PPS place diagram model. Frequency tables were created for each key concept in the themes, showing how many times the words or concepts were repeated, and word clouds of the themes were created. In addition, frequency tables and word clouds were created for the 20 most frequently repeated words that students thought were appropriate to express the concept of a child-friendly airport. In the word clouds, frequently repeated words were shown in the thickest and largest format, while words that were repeated less than others were shown in relatively thinner and displayed in small format. The larger the font, the more common the frequency or occurrence of the displayed word (Bogicevic et al., 2013). While giving direct quotations, the real names of the participants were kept confidential; instead, P1, P2, P3 were used.

4. Results and Discussion

The study group consisted of 371 students in the 13-18 age group. The distribution of students according to their age and gender is given in Table 1:

Table 1: Gender and age information of the students participating in the study

Age	Gender	Male	Female	Total
13		29	35	64
14		23	23	46
15		24	37	61
16		34	40	74
17		42	52	94
18		20	12	32
Total		172	199	371

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that there are mostly 17 (n=94), then 16 (n=74) and 13 (n=64) year old students in the study group. The least number of students aged 18 (n=32) and 14 (n=46) were in the study group. The frequency and theme statistics of the words derived by the students regarding the key concept are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Data on the themes and frequencies of the words belonging to the key concept

Disciplines	Derived Word	Total frequency
Sociability	33	642
Access/Linkages	10	339
Comfort/image	46	1661
Uses/activities	16	495
Total	105	3137

A frequency table was created with the data obtained with the independent word association test. This frequency table includes the words used for each concept and the frequency of use of each word. In this section, the word clouds created using the frequency table will be evaluated under 4 different themes. According to the table 2, students derived the most words for the theme of Comfort/Image and the least for the theme of Access/Linkages. According to the table, the highest number of words (f=1661) were related to the Comfort/Image theme.

Frequency Tables and Word Clouds Related to Themes

The word cloud for the concept of "Sociability" is given in Figure 1 and the frequency table is given in Table 3.

Figure 1. Word cloud for the theme "sociability"**Table 3.** Frequency table for the "sociability" theme

Sociability	Frequency	Sociability	Frequency
Particularly for Kids	179	Pool	8
Park	49	Recycling	8
Cartoon	47	Coloring Activities	8
Education Activities	33	Theater	8
Music	28	Green Areas	7
Food	25	Activities with Balls	7
Staff Wearing Costumes	20	Amusement Park	7
Clown	20	Book	7
Shopping	18	Raffle	7
Activities	18	Slide	6
Art	18	Concert	6
Animation	17	Educational Activities	6
Cafe	16	Trampoline	6
Television	15	All You Can Eat Buffet	5
Personalized Service	13	Scientific Activities	5
Sign Language	12	Go-kart	5
Funny Activities	8		
Total	642		

When Figure 1 and Table 3 are evaluated together, it is seen that for "Sociability" the word "Special for children" was emphasized the most (f=179), followed by "Park" (f=49), "Cartoon" (f=47) and "Educational activities" (f=33). The word cloud for the theme "Access/Linkages" is given in Figure 2 and the frequency table is given in Table 4.

Figure 2. Word cloud for the theme "access/linkages"

Table 4. Frequency table for the theme "access/linkages"

Access/Linkages	Frequency
Technology	82
Robot	69
Simulation	54
Plane	41
Security	36
Healthy food	20
Health care	14
Informative service	11
Accommodation	7
Emergency services	5
Total	339

When Figure 2 and Table 4 are evaluated together, it is seen that for "Access/Linkages" the word "Technology" is emphasized the most (f=82), followed by "Robot" (f=69), "Simulation" (f=54) and "Airplane" (f=41), respectively. The word cloud for the "Comfort/Image Theme" is given in Figure 3 and the frequency table is given in Table 5.

Figure 3. Word cloud for comfort/image theme

Table 5. Frequency table for "comfort/image theme

Comfort/Image	Frequency	Comfort/Image	Frequency
Free service	517	Fragrant	10
Hygiene	237	Purple color	10
Colorful	188	Black color	10
Services Smilingly	119	Babysitter Service	9
Fun	115	Tolerance	9
Products on Sale	42	Freedom	8
Blue color	34	Love	8
Comfort	30	Aesthetic	7
Flower	24	Rainbow	7
Secure	21	Calmness	7
Balloon	17	Respect	6
Happiness	17	Flower scent	6
Junk food	16	Fast	6
Red color	16	Big	6
Pink color	16	Helpful Personnel	5
White color	14	Cotton Candy	5
Yellow color	13	Mascot	5
Quiet	13	Adventure	5
Affordable	13	Treats	5
Spacious	12	Peace	5
Candy	12	Visual	5
Comfortable	11	Friendship	5
Chocolate	10	Drawings	5
Total	1661		

When Figure 3 and Table 5 are evaluated together, it is seen that for "Comfort/Image" the word "Free service" is emphasized the most (f=517), followed by "Hygiene" (f=237), "Colorful" (f=188) and "Friendly service" (f=119) respectively. The word cloud for the theme "Uses/Activities" is given in Figure 4 and the frequency table is given in Table 6.

Figure 4. Word Cloud for the Theme "Uses/Activities"

Table 6. Frequency Table for the Theme "Uses/Activities"

Usage/Activities	Frequency	Usage/Activities	Frequency
Playground	202	Eating Area	16
Library	38	Zoo	15
Cinema Saloon	33	Computer Area	14
Gym	32	Waiting Area	12
Field Court	30	Charging Areas	12
Sleep Area	30	Reading Areas	9
Rest Area	23	Hobby Areas	6
Museums	18	Activity and Prize Areas	5
Total	495		

When Figure 4 and Table 6 are evaluated together, it is seen that for "Uses/Activities" the word "Playground" is emphasized the most (f=202), followed by "Library" (f=38), "Movie theater" (f=33) and "Gym" (f=32) respectively. The general word cloud and the 20 most repetitive words frequency table for the word association test are given in Table 7 below:

Table 7. The 20 Most Repetitive Words in the Word Association Test

Derived Word	Frequency	Derived Word	Frequency
Free service	517	Park	49
Hygiene	237	Cartoon	47
Playground	202	Discounted products	42
Colorful	188	Airplane	41
Special for children	179	Library	38
Friendly service	119	Safety	36
It's fun	115	Blue color	34
Technology	82	Training events	33
Robot	69	Movie theater	33
Simulation	54	Gym	32

When Figure 5 and Table 7 are evaluated together, it is seen that the word "Free service" was emphasized the most in the word association test (f=517), followed by "Hygiene" (f=237), "Playground" (f=202) and "Colorful" (f=188), respectively. When Table 8 is evaluated the children most frequently referred to the word Sample expressions from the sentences written for the connotation of "free service", "hygiene". "Playground", "Colorful" are given below:

Table 8: Sentences related to the most frequently referred keywords

Free service" Sentences
"There should be free services for children at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_10)
"I want free balloons and children's food packages to make babies happy at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_12)
"Internet cafe, food and drinks should be free of charge at a child-friendly airport" (P_17)
"I would like a free playstation room at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_70)
"Let there be a free movie theater at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_74)
"Free computer space at a child-friendly airport" (P_91)
"There should be free flight simulation at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_117)
"There should be free tickets for those under 18 at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_119)
"There should be a free amusement park at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_120)
"Books should be free of charge at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_132)
"Children would be happy if free chocolate is distributed at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_134)
"Free trainings should be organized at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_138)
"There can be a free technological raffle at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_158)
"Free fun magazines should be distributed at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_159)
"There should be free go-karts at a child-friendly airport" (P_257)
"A Child Friendly Airport should have free gyms and playgrounds" (P_355)
" Hygiene" Sentences
"Everything should be clean at a child-friendly airport" (P_152)
"Hygiene should be at a high level in a Child Friendly Airport" (P_171)
"Cleanliness and hygiene are essential at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_234)
"A Child Friendly Airport should be hygienic to prevent children from getting sick" (P_283)
" Playground" Sentences
"A PS5 computer playground for children at a child-friendly airport" (P_48)
"Child Friendly Airport should have playgrounds for children of different ages" (P_146)
"The most important thing in a Child Friendly Airport is that there are different areas where people of all ages and people with disabilities can play" (P_163)
"A Child Friendly Airport should have playgrounds where children can use their talents" (P_190)
"Child Friendly Airport should have playgrounds with virtual reality glasses" (P_369)

"Colorful" Sentences

"At the Child Friendly Airport, let the planes be colorful for children who are afraid of planes" (P_115)

"There should be colorful robots at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_144)

"There should be colorful flowers at a Child Friendly Airport" (P_176)

"Children can be more positive thanks to the colorful walls at the Child Friendly Airport" (P_199)

"It would be nice if the staff at the Child Friendly Airport wore colorful clothes and had colorful planes" (P_218)

"What should definitely be in a Child Friendly Airport is friendly staff dressed in colorful clothes" (P_252)

"In a Child Friendly Airport, there should be colorful banners to inform children about everything" (P_310)

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The aim of this study is to reveal the words that 13-18 years old students associate with the concept of "child-friendly airport" and to group these words under certain categories. The findings of this study highlight some important issues. Children used a rich language to conceptually and cognitively define "child-friendly airport". In this study, the words used by the students were analyzed under 4 themes. The frequencies of the words used in the themes are "Sociability" (f=642), "Access/Linkages" (f=339), "Comfort/Image" (f=1661), "Uses/Activities" (f=495). It was found that the participants mostly used words expressed under the "Comfort/Image" theme. Among the most recurrent associations used by the students, the word associations "Free service" (f=517), "Hygiene" (f=237), "Playground" (f=202) and "Colorful" (f=188) stand out. When the sentences that the participants associated with the most recurring words are examined, the word "Free service" is associated with internet, cafe and food, beverage, playstation hall, cinema, computer area, flight simulation, ticket, amusement park, books, chocolates, trainings, technological raffles, fun magazines, go-karts, gyms and playgrounds (P10, P12, P17, P70, P74, P91, P117, P119, P120, P132, P134, P138, P158, P159, P257, P335). Fare is an important factor in passengers' choice of airports, which is in line with existing research emphasizing this result (Zhang and Xie, 2005; Tierney and Kuby, 2008; Jung and Yoo, 2016).

It is seen that they associate the word "hygiene" and perceive it as clean, high-level hygiene and hygienic to prevent children from getting sick (P152, P171, P234, P283). Every potential air traveler wants a clean airport with adequate facilities that provide comfort while waiting for the plane (Ginting & Pamuraharjo, 2024). After COVID-19, words expressing a clean and hygienic environment received higher evaluations (Li et al., 2022). "PS5 computer playground, playground for children of different ages, different areas where individuals of all ages and individuals with special needs can play, playgrounds where children can use their abilities, playgrounds with virtual reality glasses were used in sample sentences (P48, P146, P163, P190, P369). The word "colorful" was associated with colorful planes for children who are afraid of planes, colorful robots, colorful flowers, colorful walls, friendly staff dressed in colorful clothes, and banners informing children about everything (P115, P144, P176, P199, P218, P252, P310). Bogicevic et al. (2016) show that airports can create pleasant experiences if they emphasize the design aspects of terminal environments, as measured by the items that the interior wall and floor color arrangements of the airports are attractive and the airport is painted with attractive colors. As a result of the research conducted by Bogicevic, et al (2013), the words expressing the complaints and likes of the passengers were highlighted with the visualization prepared. In our research results, no negative and disliked words or terms were found among the words expressed. However, words similar to the words most commonly used by extremely satisfied passengers were found.

The keywords found by the authors reveal frequently discussed concepts and topics within a research area. When trend topic analysis based on keyword frequency is performed, it is seen that the passenger perception topic comes to the fore. Bakir et al. (2022b) airport service quality bibliometric research, the most frequently used keywords of 100 studies analyzed are visualized with a word cloud. For future research, it was suggested to investigate whether there are certain points during the airport journey that are more valuable to travelers than others (Halpern and Mwesumo, 2021). "A theoretical perspective was created with words that reveal specific points that are more valuable than others for a 'child-friendly airport'. The results of the research were obtained new conceptual definitions for "child-friendly airport" by using different words with the 'place diagram model' in the children's own voices. Therefore, it is thought that the conceptual perception of different age group users should be taken into consideration when planning child-friendly airports. It is

thought that by understanding how child-friendly airports are perceived from the perspective of children, guiding clues can be provided to predict their expectations and satisfaction. The words grouped under 4 themes in this study indicate that they should be prioritized when creating a child-friendly airport. However, the themes presented in this study are useful for understanding the relative importance of the words that 13-18 years old children associate with a child-friendly airport. It is recommended to conduct similar research with different age groups and different users. There is no conceptual study on child-friendly airports and this research is a pilot study in terms of literature contribution and awareness.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethical approval

This study was approved by the Hacettepe University Research Ethics Committee (E-35853172-300-00001948647/2021). Ethical clearance was obtained from the Senate Research and Ethics Committee at Hacettepe University. Participants were informed about the study's aims, what their participation would involve, and core ethical principles, including informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to with-draw at any time. Participants were also informed that the data collected would be used for a doctoral thesis, which would be publicly available, as well as for peer-reviewed publications and conference presentations.

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